

GUIDELINES FOR BRANDING ACCEPTABLE TO CREATE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES

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Abstract

With the change in the business environment, corporate branding is necessary to adapt the management to be effective. The purpose of this study was to investigate guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages. This study is of a mixed type research integrating both qualitative and quantitative methodology. The quantitative data were collected from 500 industrial business executives. Descriptive, referential, and multivariate statistics were used to analyse the data. It was found that the guidelines for branding acceptable consisted of four elements prioritized according to the calculated means as followed: innovation and technology, content management, channel communication and organization change, respectively. This paper utilizes the method of structural equation modelling (SEM) to establish a strategic model for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages. The analysis results indicate that the branding acceptable strategies model could help make more effective policies and organization strategies for entrepreneurs to develop business towards excellence in the world market.

Keywords: Branding acceptable; Competitive advantage; Industrial business; Innovation and technology; Content management; Channel communication; Organization change

1. INTRODUCTION

Changing economic, social, and political environments have led to increased competition in producing goods and services. As a result, many countries are looking for new strategies and approaches to gain a competitive advantage. Branding is one of the strategies; many countries adopt to lead businesses to success (Department of Industrial Promotion, 2020). Businesses and organizations focus on brand and branding activities because they will help build a reputation and image that will be recognized and remembered, create added value for products and organizations, and create added value for goods and organizations (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021). As a result, branding is the top choice that can be accessed from the customer's point of view of the quality and satisfaction of the product, as well as creating value and competitiveness (Keller and Swaminathan, 2019). In addition, branding is also a strategy to make a difference in generating consumer loyalty (Donald, 2017), and having a well-known branded business will strengthen its competitive advantage (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021). If a business has a strong brand, it can benefit many business operations, such as allowing the brand to set a premium pricing, resulting in customers paying a more

considerable amount compared to the competitor's price and being able to achieve maximum satisfaction and brand loyalty (Temporal, 2019).

According to the International Trademark Association (INTA) report in 2017, industries that take advantage of trademarks to generate significant economic benefits among ASEAN countries consist of five countries: Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand. Trademark intensive activities can encourage increased employment across all sectors and affect international trade, where industries that take advantage of trademarks in Thailand directly affect GDP by 22 percent and indirectly affect 40 percent, as well as generate up to 60 percent of the total export value (INTA, 2017). As a result, business organizations are starting to adopt branding as a marketing tool to grow a business and make a profit.

From the importance of branding above, branding is an important strategy to help create value-added and sales, and profits and business stability will follow (Kotler and Armstrong, 2021). As a result, branding has become an essential tool for building competitiveness in terms of prominence, differentiation, recognition, building a solid position, and increasing competitiveness are all important for the product's survival (Lim, Jee, and De Run, 2020). When considering the marketing of products, comparatively between branded business organizations and unbranded business organizations in both America and Britain, it found that about 70 percent of the benefits of doing business are not from investing in property. However, from intangible assets caused by branding, branding can be considered very valuable to business investment because it can be used to create value in business in many ways (Temporal, 2019).

In 2021, Thailand was the 25th exporter in the world (Trade Policy and Strategy Office, 2021). The total number of exports was 271,173.5MUSD (Trade Policy and Strategy Office, 2022), but it was found that almost no Thai brand is known in the global market. In 2020, the Forbes website ranked the top 100 most valuable brands in the world 2020 and found that the only Thai brand was Red Bull, in No.69 place in the world. Meanwhile, U.S. brands have reached the eight brands that make up the world's top 10 most valuable brands (Forbes, 2020).

In the past, entrepreneurs in Thailand have developed more branding because branding can help gain a competitive advantage with products from other countries. Nevertheless, in the past, brand development in Thailand has been low because manufacturers are only satisfied with outsourcing production to the OEM (Original Equipment manufacturer) (Office of the National Economic and Social Development Council, 2020). The problem of entrepreneurs in Thailand who cannot have their brand or cannot make their brands internationally recognized is the lack of knowledge of branding to be different and unique, as well as a lack of internationally recognized branding models (Trade Policy and Strategy Office, 2021). In addition, Thailand's brand is rarely recognized internationally. Entrepreneurs believe they still do not need to brand their products because they can currently expand the OEM production market; there is no need to pay attention to their branding (Trade Policy and Strategy Office, 2017).

Running a business to be a success, the brand is vital to manufacturers and distributors because a brand is what consumers use to discriminate against products and help generate sales for manufacturers. Consumers can adopt a brand to help reflect the level of product quality. If the organization's brand is reputable and reliable, the brand will positively affect the products associated with the same business to be famous and reliable (Donald, 2017). A brand can be considered the property of the company that specifies the company's guidelines and is a characteristic of the company's communication (Kotler and Armstrong, 2020). Therefore, branding is essential for strategizing a business to make a difference in competitiveness and self-position.

As mentioned above, running a successful business is essential to build competitiveness with branding to achieve international recognition and create competitive clauses. Therefore, researchers are interested in conducting studies to find acceptable branding practices to gain a competitive advantage, which will benefit industrial enterprises to compete internationally.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A literature review was conducted to guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages.

2.1 Innovation and Technology

Innovation is essential for entrepreneurs to create a competitive advantage, increase their company's marketing opportunities, and succeed. However, with today's rapid change in marketing communications technology, as a result, consumers are increasingly embracing information through digital media and technologies, primarily through the internet. Because of the internet media is a branding tool that can help reduce the cost of branding communications, and internet media is also a medium that can be up to date at any time, providing consumers with access to information, both in terms of information and entertainment (Solomon, 2016). In addition, consumers can interact with brands. As a result, brands have a continuous relationship with consumers, as well as get information about the characteristics of consumers. Consumer demand and consumer behavior from using the Internet, which is also beneficial for the development of brands (Kotler and Armstrong, 2020), requires organizations to develop market information systems and connect diversity to keep up with the digital world through innovative marketing communications for brand communication (Temporal, 2019).

2.2 Content management

As the market changes and the growing number of competitor's changes, the number of competitors is changing. As a result, traditional branding communication using advertising is no longer effective enough to achieve branding. Thence leads to today's business organizations needing tools to communicate brands with customers more efficiently and effectively than ever before (Duncan, 2008). Managing branded content has contributed to raising brand awareness and making a difference in generating consumer loyalty (Shimp and Andrews, 2013). Consistent with Kotler and Armstrong (2020), who stated that brand content

management had become an essential tool for building brand position and competitiveness in terms of prominence, difference, recognition, building a solid position, and increasing competitiveness are all critical to the survival of the product. Therefore, brand content management is crucial for branding.

2.3 Channel Communication

Marketing communication plays an essential role in branding and development because marketing communications help create meaning for brands, making consumers see the difference in products, helping brands maintain buyer groups, and promoting brand awareness (Kotler and Armstrong, 2020). The American Marketing Association (2007) mentioned the importance of brand marketing communications and that the brand's marketing communications make it stand out for the product's features. It is done by clear brand communication in terms of design, symbols, or anything else that can identify who the product or service belongs to, to create a clear distinction from the competitor's brand, as well as brand communication to incentivize interest in the brand and trigger the purchasing decision-making process. Brand marketing communication also includes creating a positive image in the minds of consumers and persuading consumers to support the organization's activities. (McArthur and Griffin, 1997). Communication is also a branding tool because if a brand does not communicate information to consumers, it is no different from its competitors and is not well known to consumers. In addition, brand communication channels should be selected to suit the target group and the business products. (Kapferer, 2012). Brand communication channels support branding and deliver branding messages to bring brand value to the target audience. Especially on online channels, because online is another exciting strategy for branding (Gong, 2018) and is a channel used by all brands to communicate information and activities to the target audience and enable consumers to interact with them online or on websites. The data can be stored as a database to analyze various market communication data, including consumer behavior, and is helpful for further brand development (Fill and Turnbull, 2016).

2.4 Organization change

As business organizations have begun to adopt branding as a marketing tool for businesses to grow and profit (Aghina et al. 2018), along with traditional advertising and promotions, traditional advertising and promotions are not effective enough to market today. That makes today's business organizations need more efficient and effective brand communication tools than ever before. To communicate brand information to leads (Shimp and Andrews, 2013). In the past, the activities of brand-related organizations were often understood only by marketing agencies. Thus, many organizations have structured their work by dividing it according to their functions, but as the role of "branding" has expanded to deliver a combined experience and create a sense of commitment to consumers, we have been able to do that. As a result, functional structure management may not be sufficient to meet rapidly changing consumer expectations (Keller and Swaminathan, 2019).

For the reasons mentioned above, the researcher has connected the concepts and theories to the study by four elements as follows: (1) innovation and technology; (2) content management; (3) channel communication and (4) organization change, which were later developed into the guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages.

3. HYPOTHESES AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

From the concepts and literature review above, the researcher proposes element four elements of the guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages, as shown in the hypotheses and conceptual framework in Figure 1. The subsequent hypotheses were suggested as follows:

Hypothesis 1 (H1): ‘Organization Change’ element directly influences ‘Innovation and Technology’ element.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): ‘Organization Change’ element directly influences ‘Channel communication’ element.

Hypothesis 3 (H3): ‘Innovation and Technology’ element directly influences ‘Content Management’ element.

Hypothesis 4 (H4): Innovation and technology element directly influences ‘Channel communication’ element.

Hypothesis 5 (H5): ‘Channel communication’ element directly influences ‘Content Management’ element.

Figure 1: Hypotheses and conceptual framework of the study

4. METHODS

4.1 Methodology Research

This study was designed as the mixed-methodology research of qualitative and quantitative data collection from both primary and secondary sources was employed according to the explained methods. The qualitative data were derived from an in-depth interview with nine experts with the required qualifications. The data were then used to construct questionnaires presented to 500 (Comrey and Lee, 1992) managers from Thailand's industrial business. The data from the questionnaires were then used to design the structural equation model based on the framework. The structural equation model was then validated for reliability in the focus group of eleven experts with the same criteria as the former expert group. They joined the conference to validate and certify the model for developing the implementation.

4.2 Population and Sample

The target population was the entrepreneur of the industrial businesses in Thailand. Then Names of more than 90,000 targeted companies were acquired from the database of The Office of Small and Medium Enterprises Promotion (2020), Thailand. At the same time, 500 subjects were further randomly by multi-stage sampling (Babbie, 2020) from this list that met the minimum sample size required for structural equation modelling (SEM) analysis according to Comrey and Lee's recommendation (Comrey and Lee, 1992). After passing the validation with a very good result, the questionnaires were used to collect data from 500 entrepreneurs of industrial businesses. Then, the results of the questionnaires were used to construct the simulation model.

4.3 Assessment of Research Tools

The questionnaire was primarily created from the previously published works of literature and in-depth interviews. The instrument consisted of two sections: closed-ended questions (checklist) that comprised five organization characteristics information and a 5-point Likert scale (Stockemer, 2019). of 25 questions per factor, four elements [innovation and technology; content management; channel communication and organization change]. The statement in the survey asked participants to select the level of importance that ranged from 1 (strongly unimportant) to 5 (strongly important). Before the questionnaire was sent to the participants, it was evaluated for validity and reliability. The content validity analysis was conducted through the index of item objective congruence (IOC), with the IOC values between 0.6 and 1.0 higher than the set criteria at 0.50 (Silpcharu, 2020). Five experts validated the questionnaires with a content validation between 0.60 and 1.00, All the items with less than a 0.50 IOC score were cut off from the final instrument.

The reliability value of the questionnaire was gained from the pilot study of 30 subjects to find the discriminate analysis (DA) with the DA values of the checklist items higher than the set criteria at 0.30 (Silpcharu, 2020). The rating scale items were analyzed through Cronbach's alpha with reliability higher than the set criteria at 0.80 (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). It can be concluded that the questionnaire reached very high reliability. The

discriminate analysis (DA) with the DA values of the checklist items between 0.32 and 2.00 and the DA of the question item with the correlated item-total correlation was between 0.32 and 0.79 higher than the set criteria at 0.30 (Silpcharu, 2020). The rating scale items were analyzed through Cronbach's alpha with the reliability value of 0.975, higher than the set criteria at 0.80 (Nunnally and Bernstein, 1994). Therefore, it can be concluded that the questionnaire reached very high reliability.

4.4 Data Analysis

The researcher collected questionnaires, reviewed the completeness, and used the data for analysis. The computer program with a statistical package was used. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics methods such as frequency distribution, percentage (%), mean and standard deviation (S.D.). Meanwhile, inference statistics, including Pearson's Correlation and Cronbach's alpha analyses, were performed to assess structural model validity and reliability using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science). The data were analyzed with both descriptive statistics and inferential statistics using the SPSS program. Multivariate statistical analysis and the SEM model were conducted through AMOS (Analysis of Moment Structure) to evaluate the data model fit of four values (Arbuckle, 2016). The first value is the chi-square probability level with $\rho(x^2$ or CMIN- ρ). The model consistent with data should have Chi-square in a small area p-value greater than 0.05 ($\rho > 0.05$). The ratio of Chi-square/degree of freedom (x^2/df or CMIN/DF) is the second value that must be less than 2.00 in model fitness. The goodness-of-fit index (GFI) is an indicator that required being more than 0.90 for a good fit to be indicated. The last value is a root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA); the must be lesser than 0.08 to indicate a good fit for a proper fit.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Results of Data Collection and Response Rate

The finalized questionnaire was sent to the selected participants through email. In total, 500 entrepreneurs of the industrial businesses' contributors presented a summary of the organization characteristics as shown in Table 1. The ratios of respondents were business size were 50% of the small- and medium-sized businesses and 50% of the Large sized businesses with the establishment of businesses types, mostly Company Limited (86.00%) and the Consumer products of Business sector (39.40%), the most organizations investment by Thailand investors of business capital (93.60%) with 16–20 years of business operations (55.60%) and the most industries were open for business 16 years - 20 years (55.60%).

Table 1: Summary of the organization characteristics.

General Business	Items	Frequencies (n= 500)	Percentage
Business Size	SMEs	250	50.00
	Large businesses	250	50.00
Business Types	Partnerships Limited	19	3.80
	Company Limited	430	86.00
	Public Company Limited	51	10.20
Business Sector	Agroand Food Industry	179	35.80
	Consumer Products	197	39.40
	Industrials	110	22.00
	Resources	5	1.00
	Services	5	1.00
	Technology	4	0.80
Business Capital	Investment by Thailand Investors	468	93.60
	Joint Investment between Thai Investors and Foreign Investors	32	6.40
Business Operations	5 – 10 years	34	6.80
	11 – 15 years	56	11.20
	16 – 20years	278	55.60
	>20 years	132	26.40

5.2 Results of general data analysis

The qualitative results from the in-depth interview showed that the model of branding acceptable to create competitive advantages of four elements: (1) innovation and technology; (2) content management; (3) channel communication and (4) organization change. The data were then used to write 100 questions with 25 items for each element.

The quantitative results from the samples taken from the two groups of respondents in the business size indicated that all respondents assigned high importance to the overall summary of guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages, with an average score of 4.06. When considering each aspect individually, the Organization Change element was ranked the highest with an average score of 4.08.

When considered by sample groups, analysis of the sample groups' business sizes with different, revealed significant differences in the overall guidelines and each element, with a statistical significance level of 0.05, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis

Guidelines for Branding Acceptable to Create Competitive Advantages	\bar{X}	S.D.	t-Value	P-Value
Overall	4.06	0.50	-11.12	0.00*
Innovation and Technology	4.07	0.66	-9.495	0.00*
Content Management	4.07	0.40	-11.310	0.00*
Channel Communication	4.04	0.50	-7.089	0.00*
Organization Change	4.08	0.55	-9.881	0.00*

Note: *: $p < 0.05$

5.3 Results of the structural equation model

In order to assess the validity of the developed model, the initial and revised models were compared. The results of the data model fit evaluation of the SEM model of guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages revealed that only the RMSEA value passed the set criteria, with a value of 0.055 and CMIN- ρ of 0.000, the CMIN/DF value was at 2.508, and GFI value was 0.675, both of which did not pass these criteria. Therefore, the goodness of fit was adjusted by considering modification indices derived from the program based on statistical theory, and inappropriate empirical data were deleted one by one until those four elements passed the set criteria and the model was suitable for preprocessing (Arbuckle, 2016). After all modifications, the revised model showed CMIN- ρ = 0.143 for CMIN/DF value = 1.106, GFI = 0.961, and RMSEA value = 0.015, all of which passed the model evaluation criteria and were in line with the empirical data as shown in Figure 2 and Table 3.

Table 3: Statistics after model modification

Evaluating the Data-Model Fit	Recommended value	Value of initial model	Value of revised model
CMIN- ρ	≥ 0.050	0.000	0.143
CMIN/DF	≤ 2.000	2.508	1.106
GFI	≥ 0.900	0.675	0.961
RMSEA	≤ 0.080	0.055	0.015

Figure 2: The final modified structural equation model in standardized estimate mode.

5.4 Results of Hypothesis Testing

The results of the hypothesis testing depicted as shown in Table 4, revealed that the empirical data on factors relating to ‘Organization Change’ had a direct influence on the empirical data of factors relating to ‘Innovation and Technology’ and ‘Channel Communication’ at a significance level of 0.001 with a factor loading of 0.82 and 0.55, respectively, in line with the hypothesis. The empirical data on factors relating to ‘Innovation and Technology’ had directly influenced the empirical data of factors relating to ‘Content Management’ and ‘Channel Communication’ at a significance level of 0.001 with a factor loading of 0.40 and 0.39, respectively, in line with the hypothesis. The empirical data on factors relating to ‘Channel Communication’ had directly influenced the empirical data of factors relating to ‘Content Management’ at a significance level of 0.001 with a factor loading of 0.45, respectively, in line with the hypothesis. The final refined structural equation model with standardized coefficients and factor loadings is shown in Figure 2.

Table 4: Summary of hypotheses testing results.

Variable	Estimate(β)	R ²	Variance	C.R.	P
Organization Change			0.19		
Innovation and Technology	0.82	0.68	0.11	9.401	***
Channel Communication	0.55	0.81	0.05	4.990	***
Innovation and Technology		0.68	0.11		
Content Management	0.40	0.66	0.12	3.574	***
Channel Communication	0.39	0.81	0.05	3.841	***
Channel Communication		0.81	0.05		
Content Management	0.45	0.66	0.12	3.910	***

Note: β = standardized beta coefficients; CR = critical ratio; *** $p < 0.001$

5.5 Results of Focus Group Discussion

The results of the qualitative focus group discussion of eleven experts to confirm the SEM model and discovered that the eleven experts all agreed with the consensus and confirmation that the structural equation model of guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages was valid.

6. DISCUSSION

The study's main objective was to investigate a structural equation model of guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages in Thailand. Changes in the business environment cause branding to be accepted as the key to industrial businesses. Therefore, industrial businesses should focus on effective management, especially in branding, to be accepted, which can build a reputation and revenue for the business. The critical points found in the findings of "guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages" that can be used as guidelines for branding acceptable in the industrial sector will make the enterprise successful and create sustainable competitiveness. According to the results of this research, the researchers discovered the following key points to discuss:

The research results of the significance level of the structural equation model of guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages revealed that. The Organization Change element was the highest average. Therefore, the researcher can discuss the research results as follows: Organization change; as Flanagan and Jewell (2018) explained business organizations need to have measurement and evaluation of their structure, management system, personnel, operational procedures, policies, and information systems. Consistently COSO (2020) explains that operations aimed at the efficiency and effectiveness of operations requires the

use of corporate resources operation to be economical and cost-effective. The data from this research revealed that the samples realized the importance of the organization changes, which is vital in branding to be acceptable to the organization. Therefore, the average of the organization change is the highest.

The research results of the branding approach to be acceptable to gain a competitive advantage in each aspect of the total level found that “the sample emphasized adapting branding strategies under the changing environment.” As a result, the mean score was the highest level. Peterman, Kourula, and Levitt (2020) supported that branding should be branded differently, starting by analyzing brand elements to use the data to plan to brand. It also requires constantly changing branding strategies to keep up with changing consumer behavior and the current higher business competition (Aghina et al., 2018).

When considered by sample groups, analysis of the sample group’s business size with different, revealed significant differences in the overall guidelines and each element. Interestingly, organizations can choose practical strategies to gain a competitive advantage, where performance differences within the

industry and related segments are as crucial as performance differences between each other in using organization resources (Marcus and Cohen, 2017). Confirm with McKinsey and Company (2018) that a robust large company has a high spending capacity to train and improve the organization’s personnel efficiency. Meanwhile, Aghina et al. (2018) suggested that organizations must allocate the number of personnel to suit the organization’s size and the business’s nature. According to Jeng and Pak (2016), who stated that the branding operational efficiency of large businesses is highly invested and has a complicated manufacturing process, resulting in better branding-related performance than small businesses, and large industrial enterprises have an effective management system, an ongoing branding strategy, and systematic learning and revision. Meanwhile, small and medium-sized enterprises work differently with gradual branding management characteristics (Meza–Ruiz et al., 2017). Furthermore, this is consistent with Tickle, Mann, and Adebajo’s (2016) research, which has indicated that different organizational sizes affect their ability to create competitive advantages. In addition, the relationship between successful large organizations has a positive relationship with the approach to Operational Practices, and a business performance measurement model for small and medium-sized enterprises has been developed that is different from that for larger enterprises. Nabavieh (2016) and Marcus and Cohen (2017) explain that performance differences within industries and segments are as crucial as performance differences between each other in the use of corporate resources.

The Organization Change element empirical variable directly influences on Innovation and Technology element empirical variable because Organization Change is an essential latent variable to create a competitive advantage. Internal management is vital to strengthening the organization into an advanced technology and innovation organization (Srihabut, Jariyapoom, and Roopsing, 2021). In addition, this is consistent with Arif et al. (2017), which have researched the adoption of Big Data

Analytics for branding; the organizations that succeed must have a consistent organizational strategy and branding. Furthermore, employees should be able to adapt to the existing business technology, preparing organizations and encouraging big data implementation. These factors are the main drivers of big data technology's success. However, business executives should adapt themselves, their staff, and organizations to suit the rapidly changing business, social, and technological environments and should develop and coordinate with the parties within the organization that covers the technology, information analysis, and management systems to be up to date (Aghina et al., 2018). Consistent with Dankaw and Silpcharu (2020), business organizations should be open to the policies and visions of businesses related to innovation, provide employees with access to databases, and be able to use the technologies they must use to develop knowledge and further innovation. Consistently, Bateman, Snell, and Konopaske (2020) stated that modern business organizations need to change their operating processes, development of management systems, and strategies that may be affected by changing digital technology. Also, according to Anuntaruttana and Roopsing (2020), innovation and technology are essential to business development and gaining a competitive advantage.

The organization change element empirical variable influences directly the channel communication element empirical variable, because the organization's strategy and structure affect brand communication channels and decisions about the format of brand communication channels, which in different forms of brand communication channels will result in the organization's strategy and management of brand communication channels changing (Hajli et al., 2017). In addition, Iglesias et al. (2020) said that organizations that will succeed must have consistent organizational strategies and brand communication channels. It found a correlation of related factors: technical capabilities, business capabilities, and cooperation of personnel in the organization. These factors are the main drivers of the organization's success, and the organization's executives should conduct more integrated system-related activities across agencies in the organization. In other words, employees should be involved in creating a brand image and communicating branding to outsiders (Macalik and Sulich, 2019).

The innovation and technology elements showed that the empirical variable directly influenced the content management element. This issue can be explained by the relationship between technology adoption in a company and the company's performance in an in-house context; however, as branded content management plays an increasingly important role in improving competitiveness and in branding performance, it requires the adoption of innovations and technologies that organizations must use to create engaging branded content. This research will increase the knowledge of market strategy by providing insight into the factors influencing the development of information technology capabilities (Kim and Lee, 2017). Organizations use digital technology to communicate by creating more branded content so more branded information can reach consumers (Leckie, Nyadzayo, and Johnson, 2018).

The innovation and technology element empirical variable directly influences the channel communication element empirical variable because consumer evolution leads to a wider range of

branded communication channels by adopting more innovation and technology. This point will allow consumers to use innovation and technology to find brand information through various communication channels that can be used anytime, anywhere they want (Ghezzi, Balocco, and Rangone, 2016). Research results on a wide range of communication channels affect customer satisfaction.

The purpose of this participatory quantitative study is to analyze the factors that affect the response to customer satisfaction by adjusting communication channels. Organizations that adopt digital technology to increase communication channels will receive more customer satisfaction (Otakar, Jaroslava, and Katerina, 2018). This is consistent with COSO (2020), who explains that many changes are now being made by applying blockchain to other technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT). In addition, these technologies make business operations more agile.

The channel communication element empirical variable directly influences the content management element empirical variable because to communicate brand information, products or services must know who the customer is to design the right brand content. If the substance communicates correctly to the target group, it will cause brand-supporting behavior, an intention to buy and increase sales (Gong, 2018). Consistent with Zhang et al. (2017), marketing communications are considered an effective tool in marketing but are most effective if they use marketing communication channels to target the right customers and choose the properly branded content. In addition, marketing communications are activities that raise awareness or knowledge about brands to create a brand image or a positive attitude, satisfaction, and desire for a product (Urde, 2016). Therefore, marketing communications can connect brands with customers, and branding can create a feel experience for the target consumer, including recognizing the corporate logo through marketing communications with branded content (Veloutsou and Guzman, 2017). In addition, business ethics are crucial in driving a company's success and profits; therefore, the marketer should consider ethical to consumers to sustain trust in the marketing process. However, advertisements should be created based on the product's facts and avoid misunderstandings or exaggerated content to attract consumers to buy products (Sukhawattanakun, 2022).

7. CONCLUSIONS

The research can be concluded with the model development of guidelines for branding acceptable to create competitive advantages; the four elements for developing branding acceptable are innovation and technology, content management, research channel communication, and organization change elements. An entrepreneur should adjust and develop for the extension of their business.

Industrial business entrepreneurs should adjust and develop for the extension of their business and must develop themselves to become learning organizations with sharing and exchange of knowledge to make the brand acceptable. According to the findings of this study, it is recommended that, industrial business entrepreneurs should create a database of innovations

and technologies to branding and big data databases related to brand designs for search convenience.

Entrepreneurs of industrial businesses should understand the importance of the innovation and technology for branding. At the same time, employees are authorized to access the database to utilize them for developing branding acceptable. Entrepreneurs of the industrial businesses should be aware of issues that will help to bring about brand reliability, including should be study information on the use of other corporate' brand channel communication in the past and adapting branding strategies under the changing environment. In addition, marketing strategy that will be used to create brand awareness and brand trust in the organization, enabling the organization to grow sustainably, including should be the created brand content reflecting the identity of the brand.

Moreover, this research can be further used as a guideline to create competitive advantages for the industrial sector. The researcher expects that industrial business entrepreneurs can employ this research to create a competitive advantage for the industry sustainably.

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